

An Exploration of War, Identity, and Belongingness in The English Patient

Mr. Shaikh Shaphik Kasam

Assistant Professor, Department of English, Prof. Dr. N. D. Patil Mahavidyalaya, Malakapur Perid Tal. Shahuwadi, Dist. Kolhapur 415 101 Maharashtra, India

²Author 2

Corresponding author E-mail: shaikh.shafik35@gmail.com

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Abstract

Literature portrays cultural, socio-economic, and political changes. Writers portray the influence of society on literary works. In the era of globalization, literature plays a significant role in the shaping of the culture and sustenance of harmony. Michael Ondaatje's novel, *The English Patient* portrays the culture, nationality, identity, war, and exploration of the self. The novel reflects the characters' attempt to liberate themselves from the melancholy past. It is against the Eurocentric view of postcolonialism which is predominantly ethnocentric. The novel concentrates on cultural identity and the efforts of the characters to recuperate and retain cultural identity during the ordeal of World War II.

Keywords: postcolonialism, culture, identity, war, harmony, belongingness

Philip Michael Ondaatje was born on 12th September 1943, is a Sri Lankan-born Canadian poet, fiction writer, essayist, novelist, editor, and filmmaker. *The English Patient* was published in 1992 and later was adopted into a film in 1996. The novel encompasses issues like culture, identity, war, and the efforts of characters to retain self-identity. According to Phillips, *The English Patient* highlights the conflict between the West and the East and hence acts as "a vehicle for social, political and moral reflection" (Phillips, 1999, p.121).

The objective of this research paper is to understand Sri Lankan-born Canadian writer Michael Ondaatje's *The English Patient* (1992) from the perspective of postcolonialism and social harmony. Culture plays a crucial role in fostering social harmony. The novel under study describes the cultural barrier that challenges social harmony. The writer describes the efforts of characters to explore their identity and the place to which they belong.

The novel artistically portrays a beautiful blend of cultures by bringing together heterogeneous characters in a deserted Villa of a foreign land. *The English Patient* depicts the bond of intricate relationship between four characters against the backdrop of World War II. Four major characters are, a burned man who is addressed as a patient, a Canadian army nurse, Hana; a Sikh British Army sapper, Kip; and a Canadian thief, Caravaggio. The characters have travelled far and wide and are sheltered in a ruined Villa in Italy. Bolland observes: “The central image of *The English Patient* is a figure whose identity is physically erased, made up of composite cultural influences and continually resistant to final definition.” (Bolland, 37)

Almasy is Hungarian, Hana and Caravaggio are Canadian, and Kip is Indian by birth. Despite cultural and national heterogeneity characters uphold a strong bond of humanity which is the essence of harmony and social order. The writer points out that the sharing of culture, emotions, and experiences fosters humanity and bonds people. Understanding cultural differences is always useful in overcoming several social barriers. The multicultural characters bring to foreground issues like a sense of belongingness, sense of identity, status, and recognition, and the necessity of recognizing differences with others. War, struggle for identity, and sense of belongingness or deprivation of either will disturb harmony. The effective use of multi-narrators helps the writer to develop multiple themes. The link between the past and present is formed by the use of the flashback technique. It pictures characters' endeavors to retain their identity. Don DeLillo, points out that Michael Ondaatje weaves beautiful and light-handed prose through the mingled histories of people caught up in love and war.

Villa, the opening chapter of the novel reflects on the issue of identity and culture. The nurse, Hana is serving a burned and blackened patient. Due to his accent, Almasy is assumed to be English. On the contrary, he is a Hungarian Count and desert explorer belonging to the British Cartography group. The tribe found the patient in a desert. The tribe itself does not have an identity, and like Almasy does not belong to any place. Ondaatje describes “They didn’t know my name. I didn’t know their tribe”. The tribe itself does not have a unique identity. Who are you? I don't know. You keep asking me. You said you were English”. (Ondaatje 6) In the desert, Almasy experiences a clash of cultures. Almasy meets several people from different nations. He finds Bedouins as the loveliest. Nationality is insignificant to them. Almasy wants to erase his name and the place where he comes from. In the second chapter, Michael Ondaatje describes; Caravaggio in the military hospital. Caravaggio is reluctant to reveal his identity. “During all that time, he had never spoken, communicating by signals and grimaces, now and then a grin. He had revealed nothing, not even his name, just wrote out his serial number, which showed he was with the Allies. (Ondaatje 27) In the same chapter, the writer writes about the English patient,” Who is he? He asked we don't know his name. He won't talk? The clutch of doctors laughed. No, he talks, he talks all the time, and he just doesn’t know who he is. (Ondaatje 27) Twenty years old Canadian nurse, Hana hides her identity by changing her appearance. She cuts her hair. This is an act of detaching herself from the past. Even Caravaggio is referred to as, “the man with bandaged hands” rather than by his proper name.” A conversation between Caravaggio and the English patient at the Italian Villa highlights the theme of identity and past. The English patient refers to him as “David Caravaggio-an absurd name for you, ofcourse,” To this Caravaggio answered, “At least I have a name” (Ondaatje 116)

The novel portrays the impact of war. War gives both physical and mental wounds. The novel points out that social harmony cannot be either come into existence retained in the face of war. Hana’s sufferings and predicament are caused by war. She has lost her father during the war and also the father of her unborn child. As a nurse, she never calls her patients by their names. The patient is just a “buddy” for Hana. This is emotional detachment. Kip expressed his anger and hatred of war and superpower nations. The news of the bombing of Japan upsets Kip. He expresses his anger to the Englishman. “You and then Americans converted us. With your missionary rules. And Indian soldiers wasted their lives as heroes so they could be pukkah. You had war-like cricket. How did you fool us into this? (Ondaatje, English 301)

Against the backdrop of war and disorder, the sustenance of social harmony becomes a great challenge. War always threatens social harmony, peace, and happiness. *The English Patient* encompasses the theme of war. The novel describes World War II. Almasy has fallen from the plane in the desert. The novel

highlights the physical and traumatic impact of war on individuals.

Caravaggio lost his thumb, youth, and identity. “You don’t understand. I lost my nerve. “Why?” “I was caught. They nearly chopped off my fucking hands.” (Ondaatje 33). This conversation between Hana and Caravaggio shows the horrific element of war. The war has smeared the identity of the characters. English patient has lost his identity and attempts to revive his former life.

The novel comprises an element of differences and discrimination. Any sort of discrimination and prejudice based on ethnicity is detrimental to social harmony. The British have given Kip the responsibility of destroying the bombs and mines. Kip experiences discrimination because he belongs to a different culture and has different beliefs. He is the only non-English member in the Villa. His real name is Kirpal Singh. Kip was trained by Lord Suffolk, the British nobleman to defuse the bombs and mines. This raises the feeling of belongingness in Kip. Lord Suffolk nicknamed Kirpal Singh. This displays the attempts of the English to colonize Kirpal Singh

In *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961) Frantz Fanon examines the imposition of a subjugating colonial identity as one of its sociological impacts, and it hurts the mental health of the people who were forced into colonies. Human beings desire to belong to either society, culture, religion, nation, emotion, or history. *The English Patient* concentrates on the issue of belongingness. Almsy, the English patient explores his mysterious identity and belongingness. Hana finds a sense of belongingness in her duty as a nurse. Kip returns to India and marries an Indian woman this is where he belongs. Hana, Caravaggio, and Kip returned to their homes. This is an indication of their efforts to explore the self-identification and feeling of belongingness. Lois Tyson states that individual identity “and its cultural milieu inhabit, reflect, and define each other. Their relationship is mutually constitutive (they create each other) and dynamically unstable” (Tyson 280). Harmony, love, and desire to regain cultural identity are vividly presented in the Italian Villa where they are extremely helpless. They had lost family, love, innocence, certain organs, security, and belongingness. In an interview, Ondaatje states that “there are a lot of international bastards roaming around the world today. That’s one of the book’s main stories. Those migrants don’t belong here but want to belong here” (Wachtel 257).

Conclusion

The English Patient explores subtle and complex issues like war, identity, and belongingness. The novel describes the efforts of four major characters to overcome the past and keep aside their cultural differences for the creation of social harmony. Forceful involvement of people in war endangers social harmony. Adoption of a new culture along with our own culture is helpful for social harmony.

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